

Quantum Data Augmentation for Machine Learning Classification: A Genetic Algorithm Approach for Hyperparameter Optimization of Parameterized Quantum Circuits

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Abstract

In many machine learning tasks involving tabular data, limited dataset size and class imbalance present persistent challenges to model performance. This paper introduces a quantum data augmentation framework that uses an untrained parameterized quantum circuit (PQC) to generate synthetic data samples for classical classification tasks. By applying angle encoding followed by fixed entangling operations, input vectors are mapped to quantum states and transformed into new data points through expectation value measurements, all without training the quantum circuit. Initial experiments show that this augmentation strategy can boost the performance of classical models such as Random Forest and XGBoost, often outperforming traditional techniques like SMOTE. However, the effectiveness of the synthetic samples depends heavily on the choice of PQC hyperparameters such as number of layers and samples to generate. To address this, I further introduce a Genetic Algorithm (GA) optimization layer that evolves PQC configurations to maximize downstream classifier accuracy while maintaining computation feasibility. By combining the expressiveness of PQCs with the search capabilities of evolutionary optimization, this method offers a hybrid pipeline for quantum-augmented learning. Empirical results across multiple tabular datasets demonstrate that GA-optimized PQCs can generate more impactful synthetic data, achieving higher classification accuracy than both manually selected PQCs and classical augmentation baselines.

1 Introduction

Data augmentation plays a crucial role in improving the generalization of machine learning models, particularly when training data is scarce or imbalanced. While popular augmentation strategies exist for domains like computer vision and natural language processing, tabular data presents a unique challenge. In structured datasets, simple perturbations or interpolations often fail to preserve meaningful structure, making the case for more principled augmentation strategies.

Quantum computing has recently emerged as a potential source of novel transformations for classical data. Quantum circuits can represent high-dimensional, complex transformations in relatively few parameters and are inherently capable of entangling features in ways that classical systems cannot easily replicate. These properties make them intriguing tools for data augmentation, especially in low-data regimes.

This paper explores the use of untrained parameterized quantum circuits (PQCs) for data augmentation in tabular classification tasks. The goal is to investigate whether such circuits can generate synthetic data points that, when added to the training set, improve the performance of downstream classical classifiers. Unlike previous works that rely on training quantum generative models or quantum kernels, this method keeps the PQC fixed, relying instead on its deterministic structure and entangling capability to create new data.

The core idea is simple yet effective: each input data point is first encoded into a quantum state using angle encoding via R_Y rotations, then transformed through a ring of $CNOT$ gates, and finally measured via Pauli- Z expectation values to produce a new data point. This process is deterministic and locally smooth, meaning that small changes in input lead to small changes in output, making it well-suited for label-preserving augmentation.

This method is evaluated on benchmark datasets like the Iris dataset [1], the Breast Cancer dataset [2], and the Wine dataset [3]. The results show that adding synthetic data points generated through this quantum pipeline improves performance in classical classifiers like XGBoost and Random Forest, often matching or exceeding traditional methods such as SMOTE.

However, one key challenge in this framework is the sensitivity of results to PQC hyperparameters. Namely, the number of variational layers and the number of generated samples. In the absence of an analytic way to select these parameters, they were initially explored via manual grid search, which was both extremely time consuming and computationally inefficient. To address this, I introduce a Genetic Algorithm (GA) based optimization procedure that searches the PQC configuration space to find hyperparameters that maximize classifier performance. The GA operates entirely on classical performance feedback (validation accuracy), making it a practical tool for hybrid quantum-classical optimization.

Together, the contributions offer a modular and fully classical-compatible method for quantum data augmentation and its automated tuning. The effectiveness of this approach is demonstrated on three standard datasets: Iris, Wine, and Breast Cancer, and show that GA-optimized PQCs not only outperform classical augmenters like SMOTE, but also match the best configurations found via manual tuning while requiring significantly less time.

2 Related Works

The existing literature surrounding quantum machine learning spans several complementary directions. To situate the proposed method within this landscape, the related work is organized into three categories: quantum feature maps and parameterized quantum circuits, quantum generative modeling approaches, and evolutionary optimization methods for quantum machine learning.

2.1 Quantum Feature Maps and PQCs

A central framing for quantum machine learning is that encoding classical data into quantum states can be interpreted as a nonlinear feature map into a (potentially very high-dimensional) Hilbert space, directly paralleling classical kernel methods. Schuld and Killoran [4] formalize this connection by treating the quantum state preparation (data encoding) step as the feature map

and the state overlap (inner product) as the induced kernel. They outline two complementary supervised-learning routes: an implicit approach where a quantum device evaluates a kernel that can be consumed by classical kernel methods (SVMs), and an explicit approach where a variational quantum circuit acts as a linear model in Hilbert space whose decision boundary is learned through optimization. This perspective is foundational for motivating why different quantum encodings can be viewed as “choosing a kernel,” and why quantum feature maps may yield expressive decision boundaries even with simple downstream classifiers.

Building on the same kernel/feature-space intuition, Havlíček et al. [5] propose and experimentally demonstrate supervised-learning methods that represent the feature space by a quantum state on near-term hardware. They emphasize that classical kernel methods can become limited when kernels are expensive to compute, and argue that quantum circuits can exploit large quantum state spaces via entanglement and interference. Their work presents two routes: a variational quantum classifier (analogous in spirit to learning a separating rule in feature space) and a quantum kernel estimation approach where the kernel is estimated and then used to optimize the classifier. This paper is widely cited as a concrete NISQ-era instantiation of “quantum-enhanced feature spaces,” and it motivates quantum encodings as practically testable components of supervised pipelines.

In parallel, Mitarai et al. [6] introduce Quantum Circuit Learning (QCL) as a hybrid classical-quantum framework where a low-depth parameterized circuit is trained to match labeled targets by iteratively tuning circuit parameters. They show that, with appropriate input encoding and entangling operations, PQCs can represent nonlinear functions and perform classification, while remaining compatible with near-term constraints by relying on classical optimization loops. Importantly for this paper’s context, QCL provides a general template for treating PQCs as trainable models and clarifies how nonlinearity arises through the combination of input encoding and entangling transformations, making PQCs a natural vehicle for learning in quantum feature spaces.

2.2 Quantum Generative Models and Data Augmentation

A parallel line of research in quantum machine learning has focused on quantum generative models, where parameterized quantum circuits are trained to explicitly model a target data distribution. One of the earliest and most influential proposals in this direction is quantum generative adversarial learning, introduced by Lloyd and Weedbrook [7]. In this framework, a quantum generator and discriminator engage in an adversarial game analogous to classical GANs, with convergence occurring when the generator reproduces the statistics of the true data distribution. This formulation establishes theoretical guarantees for convergence and highlights potential advantages of quantum generators when modeling high-dimensional distributions that may be difficult to sample classically.

Subsequent work by Zoufal et al. [8] extends this adversarial paradigm to practical implementations of quantum generative adversarial networks (QuGANs), focusing on learning and loading probability distributions using variational quantum circuits. These approaches emphasize gradient-based training of the generator circuit, often relying on repeated circuit evaluations and iterative updates to approximate the target distribution. While these methods demonstrate the expressive power of trained quantum generators, they also inherit many of the challenges associated with adversarial learning, including training instability, sensitivity to hyperparameters, and substantial sampling overhead.

More broadly, Benedetti et al. [9] frame parameterized quantum circuits as general-purpose machine

learning models, capable of serving as classifiers, regressors, or generative models depending on how they are trained and measured. In this view, PQCs act as trainable function approximators whose parameters are optimized via classical feedback loops. This perspective unifies a wide range of quantum machine learning proposals but also reinforces the reliance on explicit circuit training, which can be costly in the NISQ regime due to measurement noise, gradient estimation overhead, and barren plateau effects.

Closely related to adversarial approaches, Romero and Aspuru-Guzik [10] introduce variational quantum generators (VQGs) for modeling continuous classical probability distributions. Their framework employs a variational quantum circuit whose parameters are optimized, often adversarially, to match a target distribution, with samples obtained through measurement and classical post-processing. While this approach expands the scope of quantum generative modeling beyond discrete distributions, it remains fundamentally dependent on gradient-based optimization of the quantum circuit parameters.

In contrast to these generative modeling approaches, the method proposed in this work does not train the quantum circuit to approximate a data distribution. Instead, I leverage fixed, untrained parameterized quantum circuits as stochastic nonlinear feature transformations to generate synthetic samples, which are then evaluated solely through classical machine learning performance. By avoiding adversarial objectives and circuit-level training, this approach sidesteps many of the optimization challenges inherent to quantum generative models, while still exploiting the expressive structure induced by quantum encodings. This distinction positions the method closer to data augmentation and representation enhancement than to quantum generative modeling in the traditional sense.

2.3 Evolutionary and Genetic Optimization in Quantum Machine Learning

While gradient-based optimization dominates much of variational quantum machine learning, a smaller body of work has explored the use of evolutionary and genetic algorithms to optimize parameterized quantum circuits. The limited size of this literature reflects both the computational cost of evaluating quantum circuits and the historical emphasis on differentiable variational objectives. Nevertheless, evolutionary approaches provide a compelling alternative for quantum optimization problems involving discrete design choices, non-smooth objectives, or heterogeneous parameter spaces, where gradient-based methods may be ineffective.

Ding and Spector introduce Evolutionary Quantum Architecture Search (EQAS) [11], in which genetic algorithms are used to evolve the structure of parameterized quantum circuits. In their framework, circuit components such as gate types, entanglement patterns, and layer depth are encoded as chromosomes, and population-based genetic operators are applied to optimize task-specific performance. They further propose a multi-objective evolutionary framework for PQC optimization, where multiple competing objectives, such as classification accuracy, circuit depth, parameter count, and robustness considerations, are optimized simultaneously. By explicitly exploring trade-offs between performance and circuit complexity, their results demonstrate that evolutionary computation can effectively navigate complex PQC design spaces without relying on analytic gradients, highlighting the suitability of genetic representations for circuit-level optimization in quantum machine learning and their applicability to practical constraints relevant to near-term quantum devices.

Despite these advances, the evolutionary approaches in quantum machine learning primarily focus on architecture discovery and circuit-level optimization for reinforcement learning tasks. In contrast, the method proposed in this work applies genetic algorithms in a distinct role. Rather than evolving for supervised learning or reinforcement learning, evolutionary optimization was employed to tune the hyperparameters of untrained parameterized quantum circuits used exclusively for data augmentation. The fitness signal is derived solely from downstream classical classification performance, treating the quantum circuit as a fixed stochastic transformation rather than a trainable model. This reframing extends the use of evolutionary computation in quantum machine learning from circuit design to augmentation-driven hybrid learning, a setting not addressed by prior evolutionary PQC optimization methods.

3 Datasets and Preprocessing

To evaluate the effectiveness of quantum data augmentation using untrained parameterized quantum circuits, I selected three well-known tabular classification datasets from the UCI Machine Learning Repository: Iris, Wine, and Breast Cancer and applied very simple preprocessing to each.

3.1 Iris Dataset

The Iris dataset consists of 150 samples from three species of iris flowers: Setosa, Versicolor, and Virginica. Each sample is described by 4 real-valued features: sepal length, sepal width, petal length, and petal width. Unlike many prior works that reduce the dataset to a binary task, the full 3-class classification setting was retained to test the generalization capabilities of the models.

- Features: 4 (no dimensionality reduction)
- Classes: 3 (Setosa, Versicolor, Virginica)
- Preprocessing: Standardization via StandardScaler

3.2 Wine Dataset

The Wine dataset contains 178 samples of chemical analysis results from three different cultivars. Each sample includes 13 continuous features such as alcohol content, flavonoids, and proline concentration.

To enable compatibility with the limited qubit count of the quantum circuit, I reduce the feature dimensionality using Principal Component Analysis (PCA), retaining the top 6 components that explain the majority of the variance.

- Features: 6 (after PCA)
- Classes: 3
- Preprocessing: Standardization + PCA ($n_{components} = 6$)

3.3 Breast Cancer Dataset

This binary classification dataset contains 569 instances labeled as malignant or benign, with 30 numerical features derived from digitized FNA images (e.g., radius, texture, symmetry). To make this dataset compatible with quantum encoding, I apply PCA to reduce the feature space to 6 dimensions.

- Features: 6 (after PCA)
- Classes: 2 (Malignant vs. Benign)
- Preprocessing: Standardization + PCA ($n_{components} = 6$)

4 Methodology: Quantum Data Augmentation using Untrained PQCs

In this section, I propose a quantum data augmentation framework that leverages an untrained parameterized quantum circuit to generate synthetic data samples for classical machine learning classification tasks. Unlike most prior quantum machine learning approaches that focus on variationally optimizing a quantum model to learn the dataset for classification or regression, this method instead uses a fixed PQC as a nonlinear transformation engine to produce new data points that enrich the original training distribution. This generative approach aims to enhance learning performance in small or imbalanced tabular datasets.

Figure 1. Overview of the proposed quantum data augmentation framework. Classical input data are encoded into quantum states using angle encoding, transformed through a fixed untrained parameterized quantum circuit, measured via expectation values to generate synthetic samples, and concatenated with the original dataset for downstream classical classification.

The augmentation process begins by selecting a classical dataset and standardizing its features. Given a sample $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$, where d denotes the number of features, angle encoding is used to map the input into a quantum state. Specifically, each feature x_i is encoded into a single qubit via a Y -axis rotation $R_Y(x_i)$, resulting in the initial state

$$|\Psi(x)\rangle = \left(\prod_{i=0}^{d-1} R_Y(x_i) \right) |0\rangle.$$

This form of amplitude-free encoding is chosen for its simplicity and for preserving the dimensional correspondence between classical and quantum representations, with one qubit per feature. The encoded state thus retains the structure of the input while enabling interaction with the exponentially large Hilbert space of the quantum system.

After encoding, the quantum state is passed through a parameterized quantum circuit composed of multiple layers of trainable rotations and entangling gates. However, in this baseline framework, the parameters of the PQC are not trained. Instead, they are initialized randomly from a normal distribution and remain fixed throughout the entire experiment. This design choice follows the hypothesis that fixed, randomized circuits can serve as universal feature maps, implicitly performing nonlinear transformations on the data. Each layer of the PQC contains single-qubit $R_Y(\theta)$ rotations on each qubit, followed by entangling operations using $CNOT$ gates arranged in a ring topology. That means qubit i is entangled with qubit $(i + 1) \bmod d$, enabling correlations across features. The total number of trainable parameters in the PQC is $L \times d$, where L is the number of layers and d is the number of qubits. Despite the lack of training, the depth and structure of the circuit inject significant expressive power, allowing it to generate transformed versions of the original data that lie in a complex, high-dimensional manifold.

Once the quantum circuit is applied, the final state is measured to extract a real-valued synthetic sample. The expectation value of the Pauli- Z operator, $\langle Z_i \rangle$, is measured on each qubit i , yielding a continuous vector $x' \in \mathbb{R}^d$, where each entry lies in the range $[-1, 1]$. This measurement process compresses the quantum state back into classical space while preserving the correlations and transformations applied by the PQC. The measured vector x' serves as a synthetic data point with the same dimensionality as the original input.

To create a synthetic dataset, this process is repeated N times: at each iteration, a real training sample x is selected at random, passed through the fixed PQC, and measured to produce x' . The resulting collection of vectors forms a new quantum synthetic dataset $X_{\text{quantum}} \subset \mathbb{R}^{N \times d}$.

Since the approach is fully unsupervised (the PQC has no knowledge of class labels), labels are assigned to the synthetic samples by inheriting the original training labels. This label assignment mechanism preserves class balance and prevents the model from introducing unrealistic class skew into the augmented data. The final augmented training set is then constructed by concatenating the original and synthetic data:

$$X_{\text{aug}} = X_{\text{train}} \cup X_{\text{quantum}} \quad y_{\text{aug}} = y_{\text{train}} \cup y_{\text{synthetic}}$$

This augmented dataset is subsequently used to train a classical classifier. In the experiments, XGBoost and Random Forest classifiers are utilized with default settings (no model tuning), and performance is compared across three versions of each model: one trained on the original training set (baseline), one trained on data augmented with SMOTE (a standard oversampling technique), and one trained on data augmented using the quantum method. Final evaluation is conducted on an untouched test set to measure generalization performance.

The methodology provides a hybrid approach to quantum machine learning, where quantum circuits are used solely for data generation rather than inference. This design decouples the quantum component from the downstream task, making it modular and broadly compatible with any classical model.

5 Results: Quantum Data Augmentation using Untrained PQCs

To evaluate the performance impact of quantum-generated synthetic data, a grid of PQC configurations was manually explored using a sweep over the number of circuit layers ($n_{\text{layers}} \in [2, 6]$)

and the number of generated samples ($n_{samples} \in [100, 5000]$ in steps of 100). This was extremely computationally intensive, motivating the later proposal of a Genetic Algorithm. For each configuration, synthetic data were produced using untrained PQCs and appended to the training set prior to model training. Performance was compared against baseline models trained on the original data, as well as SMOTE-based data augmentation. The two classification models used were XGBoost and Random Forest. The corresponding accuracy and relative gain over baseline are reported for each dataset and model pairing.

5.1 Iris Results

Random Forest: The baseline accuracy was 88.8%, and SMOTE provided no improvement (also 88.8%). In contrast, quantum augmentation increased accuracy to 93.3%, yielding a +4.5% absolute gain over the baseline.

XGBoost: The baseline and SMOTE-augmented models both achieved 93.3%, indicating no measurable improvement. However, the quantum-augmented model reached 95.5%, corresponding to a +2.2% absolute increase.

5.2 Wine Results

Random Forest: The baseline accuracy was 90.7%, while SMOTE slightly reduced performance to 88.8%. In contrast, quantum augmentation substantially increased accuracy to 98.1%, yielding a +7.4% absolute gain over the baseline. This represents the largest improvement observed across all experimental settings.

XGBoost: The baseline and SMOTE-augmented models both achieved 90.7%, indicating no measurable improvement. With quantum augmentation, accuracy increased to 96.2%, corresponding to a +5.5% absolute gain.

5.3 Breast Cancer Results

Random Forest: The baseline model achieved 93.5% accuracy, with SMOTE providing a modest increase to 94.1%. Quantum augmentation outperformed both approaches, reaching 96.4%, corresponding to a +2.9% absolute gain over the baseline.

XGBoost: The strongest baseline performance across all experiments was observed here at 95.9%, with SMOTE further improving accuracy to 97.0%. The quantum-augmented model slightly surpassed both, achieving 98.2%, representing a +2.3% absolute increase over baseline.

6 Overview: Genetic Algorithm for Optimization of PQC Hyperparameters

While the base quantum data augmentation framework demonstrates performance gains over classical oversampling methods, its effectiveness hinges critically on the choice of PQC hyperparameters

(the number of circuit layers, the number of generated samples, the combination of rotation gates used, and the entanglement pattern). In the initial experiments, a brute-force grid search was relied upon across two parameters: number of layers and number of samples. This search was limited to a fixed rotation type (R_Y) and a single entanglement structure (*ring*), due to the high computational overhead associated with broader experimentation.

However, this manual grid-based approach was both time-consuming and rigid, requiring extensive and often infeasible amount of computational resources to fully evaluate even a coarse sweep, and inherently unable to explore intermediate or non-discretized values (sample sizes between fixed step sizes). It also could not scale to include more expressive PQC variations, such as combinations of R_X , R_Y , and R_Z rotations or alternative entanglement schemes.

To overcome these limitations, a Genetic Algorithm (GA) is introduced as an efficient and scalable optimization framework for PQC hyperparameters. A GA is a stochastic, population-based metaheuristic inspired by natural selection. It evolves a population of PQC configurations (“individuals”) over successive generations, using genetic operators like crossover and mutation, and evaluates them using a fitness function derived from downstream model performance.

Figure 2. Genetic Algorithm optimization loop used to tune PQC hyperparameters for quantum data augmentation. Each individual encodes a PQC configuration (layers, rotation gates, entanglement pattern, and number of synthetic samples). Fitness is computed as downstream classifier accuracy, and elitist ($\mu + \lambda$) selection forms the next generation.

By encoding PQC configurations as chromosomes and using validation accuracy as the fitness score, the GA is able to intelligently search the full hyperparameter space including rotation combinations and entanglement topologies without requiring exhaustive enumeration. This results in significant speedups: the GA can identify near-optimal configurations much more tractably, a substantial improvement over brute-force grid search. Moreover, it can discover parameter values at a finer resolution than a manually predefined grid, such as integer values within the step size, making it a powerful tool for tuning this parameterized quantum circuit.

A genetic algorithm is particularly well-suited for this optimization problem due to the discrete, heterogeneous, and non-differentiable nature of the PQC hyperparameter space. The fitness signal (downstream classification accuracy) is a black-box objective that is both expensive to evaluate and lacks analytic gradients. Moreover, the search space includes categorical choices such as rotation gate combinations and entanglement topology, which are not naturally handled by gradient-based

or surrogate optimization methods. Population-based evolutionary search allows for efficient exploration of this mixed parameter space while naturally balancing exploration and exploitation. For these reasons, a genetic algorithm provides a practical and scalable solution for tuning untrained PQC configurations.

7 Methodology: Genetic Algorithm for Optimization of PQC Hyperparameters

To automate and accelerate the discovery of effective PQC configurations, a Genetic Algorithm was implemented using the *DEAP*[12] evolutionary computation Python library. Each individual in the GA population represents a unique PQC configuration encoded as a list of four integer-valued genes. These genes include the number of circuit layers (n_{layers}), the number of synthetic data samples to generate ($n_{samples}$), the type of quantum rotation gates applied (*rotation type*), and the pattern of entanglement used in the circuit (*entangle type*). The rotation type encodes one of seven possible combinations of R_X , R_Y , and R_Z rotations, while the entangle type indicates whether a *ring* or *full* entanglement structure is applied. This compact yet expressive representation allows the GA to evolve a diverse set of PQC architectures.

The fitness of each individual is evaluated based on the classification accuracy of a downstream classical machine learning model trained on data augmented using the individual’s PQC configuration. For each individual, synthetic data are generated using an untrained parameterized quantum circuit with the specified structure and appended to the training set. A classical classifier (XGBoost or Random Forest) is then trained on this augmented data and evaluated on a held-out test set. The resulting test accuracy serves as the fitness score for the individual. This setup ensures that PQC configurations yielding useful synthetic data naturally receive higher fitness values, guiding the evolutionary process toward more effective augmenters.

For parent selection, tournament selection with a tournament size of 3 was used, balancing selective pressure with population diversity. Offspring are created using uniform crossover with a crossover probability of 0.9, meaning 90% of the time crossover occurs and each gene has a 50% chance of being inherited from either parent. This method allows flexible recombination of architectural features and is well-suited for problems involving heterogeneous parameter types. To introduce variability, a Gaussian-inspired integer mutation operator was applied with a mutation probability of 0.3. Each gene independently has a chance of being perturbed by a small integer drawn from a normal distribution centered at zero. The mutated value is then clipped to remain within the allowable bounds of each parameter. This mutation strategy avoids large random jumps and instead enables finer-grained local exploration around promising solutions.

The evolutionary process uses a $(\mu + \lambda)$ elitist selection strategy, where the best individual from the current generation (elitism size = 1) is preserved and combined with newly generated offspring to form the next generation. This helps retain the strongest solution while allowing new variations to be explored for diversity maintenance. A population size of 15 was used and the GA was run for 10 generations, resulting in a total of 150 model evaluations. These settings were chosen to balance computational budget with search depth, especially in contrast to manual grid search methods that can require thousands of evaluations.

This combination of structured representation, performance-based fitness evaluation, and evolution-

ary operators provides an efficient way to tune PQC hyperparameters automatically. Compared to manual tuning, the GA explores the search space more thoroughly, discovering effective configurations in significantly less time and often identifying parameter combinations that manual sweeps might overlook due to rigid step sizes.

8 Results: Genetic Algorithm for Optimization of PQC Hyperparameters

To assess the effectiveness of the Genetic Algorithm in optimizing PQC hyperparameters for quantum data augmentation, the GA-optimized results were compared against both manually tuned PQC configurations and classical baselines (with and without SMOTE augmentation) across three standard tabular datasets: Iris, Wine, and Breast Cancer. For each dataset, both Random Forest and XGBoost classifiers were trained and evaluated on the test accuracy after augmentation. In every single case, the GA-optimized quantum augmentation either matched or outperformed the manually tuned variant.

Table 1. Test Accuracy (%) Comparison Across Augmentation Methods

Dataset	Model	Baseline	SMOTE	Manual PQC	GA-PQC
Iris	Random Forest	88.8	88.8	93.3	95.5
	XGBoost	93.3	93.3	95.5	95.5
Wine	Random Forest	90.7	88.8	98.1	98.1
	XGBoost	90.7	90.7	96.2	98.1
Breast Cancer	Random Forest	93.5	94.1	96.4	97.6
	XGBoost	95.9	97.0	98.2	98.2

In the Iris dataset with Random Forest, the GA-discovered configuration achieved 95.5% accuracy, outperforming the manual quantum augmentation (93.3%) by +2.2%, and the baseline (88.8%) by +6.7%. This illustrates the GA’s ability to locate better performing PQC settings that manual search may overlook.

For the Wine dataset, the GA achieved the highest absolute gain: the XGBoost model improved from 90.7% (baseline) and 96.2% (manual) to 98.1%, a +7.4% increase. Similarly, the Random Forest model for Wine matched its best manually tuned quantum accuracy at 98.1%, confirming that the GA could discover optimal solutions without exhaustive grid sweeps.

The Breast Cancer dataset showed consistent but smaller improvements. The GA-enhanced Random Forest model reached 97.6%, surpassing the manually tuned model (96.4%) by +1.2%, while the XGBoost model maintained its peak performance of 98.2% under both manual and GA-based PQC configurations.

Importantly, these gains were achieved with significantly lower computational cost than manual grid search. Manual tuning required significant computation per dataset due to its discrete, fixed-step evaluation of the hyperparameters. In contrast, the GA typically converged to optimal or near-optimal solutions in much less computational effort and could explore a finer, more continuous

space of hyperparameters, including combinations not present in the manually defined search grid.

These results validate the value of using evolutionary optimization for PQC hyperparameter selection, offering both performance gains and computational efficiency. Moreover, this approach is broadly applicable as a scalable optimization framework for quantum machine learning, where the exponential complexity of simulating or tuning quantum circuits makes traditional exhaustive search strategies computationally prohibitive. GA-based optimization provides a practical and generalizable alternative for hyperparameter tuning in quantum workflows.

9 Key Takeaways, Limitations, and Future Work

This work demonstrates that untrained parameterized quantum circuits can act as effective nonlinear data augmentation mechanisms for classical machine learning models operating on tabular data. Even without variational training, PQC-based transformations consistently improve downstream classification performance and often outperform classical oversampling methods such as SMOTE. Additionally, the results highlight that evolutionary optimization provides an efficient and reliable strategy for selecting PQC hyperparameters in the absence of analytic gradients or closed-form performance guarantees.

By decoupling quantum circuits from model training and inference, this framework lowers the barrier to incorporating quantum transformations into classical learning pipelines. The approach avoids common challenges associated with training quantum models, such as barren plateaus and high simulation cost, while still leveraging the expressive structure of quantum circuits. This makes quantum data augmentation a practical tool in near-term hybrid quantum-classical workflows, particularly in low-data or structured-data regimes.

The proposed method relies on classical simulation of quantum circuits, which limits scalability as the number of qubits increases. Additionally, while the augmentation strategy preserves labels by construction, the theoretical guarantees regarding distributional fidelity and class boundary preservation remain an open question. The experiments are also restricted to a small set of benchmark datasets and classical models, and broader evaluation is needed to fully characterize generalization behavior.

Future research directions include extending this framework to larger feature spaces as quantum simulators and hardware improve, exploring alternative encoding schemes and entanglement structures, and evaluating the method on more diverse real-world tabular datasets. Another promising direction is integrating adaptive or dataset-aware evolutionary objectives that balance performance gains with computational cost. Finally, deploying the augmentation pipeline on actual quantum hardware would allow investigation of noise-induced effects and potential quantum advantages beyond classical simulation.

10 Conclusion

This work introduced a quantum data augmentation pipeline using an untrained parameterized quantum circuit (PQC) and demonstrated its effectiveness in enhancing the performance of classical machine learning classifiers on structured tabular data. By transforming classical samples into

synthetic data via randomized PQC transformations and expectation-value measurements, high-quality augmentations were generated that rival and often exceed those produced by traditional methods such as SMOTE.

However, the success of this augmentation is highly sensitive to the choice of PQC hyperparameters, including the number of layers, number of synthetic samples, gate rotations, and entanglement patterns. To address this, a Genetic Algorithm (GA) was developed to efficiently search this hyperparameter space using a performance-driven fitness function. Compared to brute-force manual tuning, which is computationally intensive and restricted by discretized parameter steps, the GA approach converges with lower computational overhead while exploring a finer continuous configuration space. This optimization was achieved using a population-based search, uniform crossover, Gaussian integer mutation, tournament parent selection, and elitist ($\mu + \lambda$) survivor selection.

Empirical results across the Iris, Wine, and Breast Cancer datasets show that GA-optimized PQCs match or outperform both classical and manually-tuned quantum baselines in every case. These findings validate the utility of evolutionary algorithms for navigating complex quantum configuration spaces and point to a scalable methodology for future work in quantum data processing and quantum machine learning. As quantum systems become increasingly advanced, genetic algorithms will play a critical role in tuning parameters efficiently within hybrid quantum-classical pipelines.

References

- [1] R. A. Fisher. Iris. UCI Machine Learning Repository, 1936. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.24432/C56C76>.
- [2] William Wolberg, Olvi Mangasarian, Nick Street, and W. Street. Breast Cancer Wisconsin (Diagnostic). UCI Machine Learning Repository, 1993. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.24432/C5DW2B>.
- [3] Stefan Aeberhard and M. Forina. Wine. UCI Machine Learning Repository, 1992. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.24432/C5PC7J>.
- [4] Maria Schuld and Nathan Killoran. Quantum machine learning in feature hilbert spaces. *Physical Review Letters*, 122(4), February 2019.
- [5] Vojtěch Havlíček, Antonio D. Córcoles, Kristan Temme, Aram W. Harrow, Abhinav Kandala, Jerry M. Chow, and Jay M. Gambetta. Supervised learning with quantum-enhanced feature spaces. *Nature*, 567(7747):209–212, March 2019.
- [6] K. Mitarai, M. Negoro, M. Kitagawa, and K. Fujii. Quantum circuit learning. *Physical Review A*, 98(3), September 2018.
- [7] Seth Lloyd and Christian Weedbrook. Quantum generative adversarial learning. *Physical Review Letters*, 121(4), July 2018.
- [8] Christa Zoufal, Aurélien Lucchi, and Stefan Woerner. Quantum generative adversarial networks for learning and loading random distributions. *npj Quantum Information*, 5(1), November 2019.
- [9] Marcello Benedetti, Erika Lloyd, Stefan Sack, and Mattia Fiorentini. Parameterized quantum circuits as machine learning models. *Quantum Science and Technology*, 4(4):043001, November 2019.

- [10] Jonathan Romero and Alan Aspuru-Guzik. Variational quantum generators: Generative adversarial quantum machine learning for continuous distributions, 2019.
- [11] Li Ding and Lee Spector. Multi-objective evolutionary architecture search for parameterized quantum circuits. *Entropy*, 25(1):93, January 2023.
- [12] Félix-Antoine Fortin, François-Michel De Rainville, Marc-André Gardner, Marc Parizeau, and Christian Gagné. DEAP: Evolutionary algorithms made easy. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 13:2171–2175, jul 2012.